

1 **Title:** Ranking spatial areas by risk of cancer: modelling in epidemiological
2 surveillance.

3

4 **Authors:**

5 Pablo Fernández-Navarro^{1,2,3,*}, Javier González-Palacios^{1,3}, Mario González-
6 Sánchez^{1,3}, Rebeca Ramis^{1,2}, Olivier Nuñez^{1,2}, Francisco Palmí-Perales⁴, Virgilio
7 Gómez-Rubio⁴

8

9 **Affiliations:**

10 ¹Cancer and Environmental Epidemiology Unit, Department of Epidemiology of
11 Chronic Diseases, National Center for Epidemiology, Carlos III Institute of Health,
12 Avda. Monforte de Lemos, 5, 28029 Madrid, Spain

13 ²Consortium for Biomedical Research in Epidemiology & Public Health (CIBER en
14 Epidemiología y Salud Pública -CIBERESP), Spain

15 ³Bioinformatics and Data Management Group (BIODAMA), Department of
16 Epidemiology of Chronic Diseases, National Center for Epidemiology, Carlos III
17 Institute of Health, Avda. Monforte de Lemos, 5, 28029 Madrid, Spain

18 ⁴Department of Mathematics, School of Industrial Engineering - Albacete, Universidad
19 de Castilla-La Mancha, Avda. España, s/n, 02071, Albacete, Spain.

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Abstract

Background: The representation and analysis of maps of events within a fixed time frame/period is established as a basic tool for disease monitoring, where apart from having methods that can address the study of certain problems, the existence of criteria to discriminate relevant results is equally important. In chronic diseases such as cancer, monitoring by studying the spatial distribution of mortality/morbidity in small areas through relative risk estimators is frequent, but there is no clear strategy in public health to discriminate which regions are important. Moreover, it usually requires too much time for an effective surveillance or an advanced technical knowledge. The objectives are to establish a pipeline of analysis that allows to make an initial screening that discriminate regions of interest in the context of chronic diseases monitoring and develop a R-Shiny application to implement this strategy in a simple way, fast and without a deep technical knowledge.

Methods: First, a pipeline of seven steps for ranking risk of disease spatial areas was developed taking into account relative and absolute risk estimators, using observed and expected cases in spatial units of a study region. Second, a R-Shiny application (RANSKPA, Ranking Spatial Areas) was developed to perform the pipeline. And third, we applied the pipeline using RANKSPA to simulated data and real data (lung cancer municipal mortality 2005-2009 in Galicia (North-East of Spain), 314 spatial units).

Results: There is a clear excess of mortality in the middle-east of the studied region using simulated data where a spatial mortality cluster is also located, existing 5 spatial units outside this cluster that occupy the top positions in the ranking generated by the application. From the total spatial units of the study region (314), only 14 have an excess of mortality whose posterior probabilities are greater than or equal to 80%. And all the spatial tests implemented except the Moran's I test are statistically significant. In the study of real data, it is observed that there is a clear excess of mortality in the east of the studied region where several of the spatial mortality clusters are also located and there are 3 spatial units located outside these clusters that occupy the top positions in the ranking generated by the application. 11 spatial units have an excess of mortality whose posterior probability is greater than or equal to 80%. And all the spatial tests implemented are statistically significant. Both, in simulated and real data, there is a positive correlation between absolute and relative measures. However, a greater dispersion is observed when these measures take the highest values.

Conclusions: the work presented shows a strategy of analysis to implement an initial screening of disease risk that allows to discriminate regions of interest by studying the spatial distribution in small areas, focused primarily on chronic diseases such as cancer. Furthermore, a shiny application that has been created to be able to implement this strategy easily without great technical knowledge.

Keywords:

Spatial analysis; Ranking; Epidemiological surveillance; Ranking application; Screening; Cancer

1 Introduction

2
3 Public health surveillance includes a wide range of monitoring methods, being the
4 spatial or spatio-temporal study of the diseases a reasonable starting point for any
5 grounded health intervention. Likewise, strategies that employ or integrate different
6 statistical methods could be relevant to best aid the task of this surveillance.
7

8 The spatial surveillance merge monitoring statistics for evidence of a change
9 and spatial techniques which are often used to find or describe the extent of clustering
10 across a map. Other idea related to spatial surveillance is that of screening. It could be
11 applied to populations as well as individuals (1), where the location of the public health
12 event is as important as the fact that it occurred. Surveillance and screening carried out
13 at an aggregate population level (ej. municipality, census track, ...), could be useful to
14 detect passing limits based on observed or expected patterns, to know where the health
15 incidents occur, and possibly allowing to anticipate where they will occur. All of these
16 might trigger interventions designed for example to redirect health resources towards
17 attempts to improve the health status of the population as well as it can be useful for
18 prevention programs.
19

20 The representation and analysis of maps of events within a fixed time
21 frame/period is established as a basic tool for disease monitoring. In this context, there
22 is a wide range of methods that can be applied, such as disease mapping, spatial
23 clustering or ecological analysis, each of them appropriate to answer specific questions,
24 and that usually requires advanced technical knowledge (programming, statistics, ...) to
25 be implemented. In that way, there are valuable applications or statistical packages
26 such as “*GeoDa*” software (2) or “*SSTCDapp*” (3), but above all, the shiny web
27 application “*SpatialEpiApp*” (4), that allow us to perform these methods in a simple
28 way and without extensive technical knowledge.
29

30 Furthermore, in spatial surveillance, apart from having specific methods , it is
31 equally important the existence of a criteria to discriminate relevant results. For
32 example, in disease mapping that usually involve Bayesian models to smooth the
33 underlying risk estimates, the distribution of the posterior probability (PP) that the
34 Relative Risk larger than 1 (Bayesian method to assess high risk) is used. Insofar as this
35 indicator was concerned, it is usually to follow Richardson's criterion (5), which
36 recommends that probabilities above 0.8 should be deemed significant. Although this
37 approach can improve the discrimination between areas of interest based on the relative
38 risk, in the context of public health and surveillance the methods should consider
39 absolute measures related for example with size of the expected counts or other
40 approaches to rank risk estimates with pp higher than 80%.
41

42 In chronic diseases such as cancer, studying the spatial distribution of mortality
43 or morbidity in small areas through relative risk estimators is very frequently used for
44 monitoring (6–11). In this sense, cancer mortality or incidence atlas (12–15) are very
45 useful tools. Nevertheless, on many occasions, the time required for conducting these
46 analyzes or atlases is usually too long for effective surveillance or to develop
47 interventions and address problems in time. In addition, there is no clear strategy to
48 discriminate which regions are important both from the point of view of relative
49 estimators and of absolute estimators that in matters of public health are very important.
50

1 Accordingly, the objectives of this work are: 1) to establish a pipeline of
2 analysis that allows us to discriminate regions of interest in the context of chronic
3 diseases (such as cancer) monitoring by studying the spatial distribution in small areas
4 of mortality / morbidity, attending to relative and absolute risk estimators and the
5 precision of them, obtaining a ranking of spatial units, thus being able to implement an
6 initial spatial screening useful in epidemiological surveillance and public health and 2)
7 to present the shiny application that has been created to be able to implement this
8 strategy in a simple way, fast and without a deep technical knowledge of the statistical
9 and programming methods necessary to perform it.

12 **Methods**

14 In order to achieve the objectives, several spatial analyses with the calculation of
15 relative and absolute estimators were conducted to identify and rank areas of risk of a
16 disease where the distribution of it in a study area is divided into several non-
17 overlapping smaller regions. The analyses, that arise, start from the moment when a
18 measure of observed and expected cases and the population is already available for each
19 of the study regions.

21 As a result, a pipeline of analysis including the strategies followed to rank risk
22 areas has been established as indicated in *Figure 1* and described below. And finally,
23 we show the Shiny web application for ranking spatial areas of risk in spatial
24 surveillance “*RANKSPA*” to perform the pipeline and what results are obtained by
25 applying this to non-real data as an example and to a real data of municipal lung cancer
26 mortality.

28 ***Pipeline for ranking spatial areas***

30 The analyzes that are presented in this work deal with modelling areal data (observed
31 cases on polygons entities with defined boundaries). In these analyses the spatial
32 autocorrelation among areal entities should be taken into account. In that way, the **first**
33 **step** in the pipeline is to create the neighbourhood structure using a standard neighbour
34 criterion, the contiguity, where all touching polygons are neighbours. For this purpose,
35 “*poly2nb*” function of the “*spdep*” R package could be applied (16,17).

37 As part of any spatial data analysis, a series of statistical tests should be applied
38 to assess overdispersion, spatial autocorrelation and general spatial clustering. These
39 analyzes constitute the **second step** and the results will enrich the ranking process that
40 will be discussed later. First of all, the spatial heterogeneity of the risk measures is
41 assessed, testing for global significant differences between observed and expected cases.
42 The reason of a possible heterogeneity may be related to many different factors, such
43 as the presence of different medical assistance systems or pollution sources in the areas.
44 Two common tests of overdispersion are used in this step; the standard Chi-square test
45 and the Potthoff-Whittinghill's test (see the parametrization described in pages 348-349
46 of the Bivand RS. et al. book (17)). “*achisq.test*” and “*pottwhitt.test*” functions of the
47 “*DCluster*” R package (18) could be used to performed them. Moreover, two common
48 tests of global clustering, Moran I test and Tango’s test, are also performed in this step
49 to assess global spatial autocorrelation. “*moranI.test*” and “*tango.test*” functions of the

1 “DCluster” R package (18) could be applied to performed these tests (see pages 350-
2 352 of the Bivand RS. et al. book (17)).

3
4 In the **third step** of the proposed pipeline, a standard test (Kuldorff and
5 Nagarwalla test (19)) for the detection of spatial clusters based on a circular window is
6 applied. We selected this approach because it is a well-established method in this field,
7 easy to implement and with a relatively low computational cost, although it has several
8 limitations as will be discussed later. The results from this analysis will enrich, with
9 relevant information for spatial surveillance, the ranking of the risk areas that is the
10 final result of the application of this pipeline. “*opgam*” function of the “DCluster” R
11 package could be applied to performed this test (see pages 353-354 of the Bivand RS.
12 et al. book (17)). To define the window in this detection of spatial clusters, the
13 maximum fraction of the total population inside the cluster could be used. This
14 parameter should be changed to assess if the location of clusters varies significantly.
15 Moreover, only clusters with p-values lower than 0.05 will be taken into account.

16
17 The **fourth step** consists in a initial calculation of local relative risk (RR)
18 estimators of disease and the distribution of the posterior probability (PP) that $RR > 1$
19 (Bayesian way to assess high). To do this, based on the data to be analysed, conditional
20 autoregressive model proposed by Besag, York and Mollié (BYM) (8,20,21) would be
21 used. This model is based on fitting a Poisson spatial model with observed cases as the
22 dependent variable, expected cases as offset, and two types of random effect terms
23 which take the following into account: a) contiguity (spatial autocorrelation term); and
24 b) spatial heterogeneity. For more details see the article of López-Abente G. et al. (8).
25 As a tool for Bayesian inference, we recommend to use the Integrated nested Laplace
26 approximations (INLAs) (22). The reason for this approach is that it allows to obtain
27 reliable results in a reasonable time and at much lower computational cost, when
28 compared to the more traditional Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method (23–
29 25). “*inla*” function of the R-INLA package (26,27) with the option of simplified
30 Laplace estimation of the parameters could be used to perform the models. Finally, in
31 this **fourth step**, with the estimators, RR and PP for each spatial area, we calculated a
32 weighted Relative Risk (WRR) consisted in multiplying each RR by its PP, this way
33 the relative risk measure is penalize by the precision of the estimation. Fact that could
34 help to discard some non-significant results.

35
36 The step of the pipeline before ranking the spatial areas of risk, **the fifth step**,
37 consisted in the calculation of an absolute measure of risk that is defined as the
38 difference between observed and expected cases (DOE).

39
40 Finally, the last step of the pipeline, **the sixth step** consists first in the
41 identification of those areas where PP are higher than 80% (Richardson's criterion (5))
42 and those lower than 80%. The areas in the first group, will be ranked attending first at
43 the DOE and after to the WRR assigning them a numerical value starting at 1 that marks
44 the highest level of importance. It means the highest DOE with the highest WRR. All
45 the spatial areas where PP are lower than 80% will have the same rank value and will
46 be the highest numerical value assigned to the spatial areas of the first group plus one.

47
48 The final result of the pipeline, is a ranked table of spatial areas attending to
49 absolute and relative risk estimators and enriched with useful information of global and

1 local clustering and spatial heterogeneity to understand the ranking. And it constitutes
2 a rapid initial screening to identify areas of interest for public health.

3
4 An R script (“*R_script.R*”) is provided to perform the pipeline. Simulated data
5 (“*data_example.xlsx*”) of observed and expected cases in 314 spatial areas and a
6 shapefile (“*map_example.zip*”) are also provided for the application of the script. See
7 section “*Code and Data availability*” of the manuscript.

10 ***RANKSPA app***

11
12 In the same way other that authors try to give useful applications for spatial analysis or
13 data management (3,4) and allow to make statistical methods in a simple way and
14 without extensive technical knowledge, we create a R-Shiny web application called
15 RANKSPA (“*RANKing SPatial Areas*”) that allow to perform the pipeline describe
16 before. In that way, RANKSPA allows to obtain a ranking of spatial areas attending to
17 absolute and relative disease risk. RANKSPA R-shiny code is provided (see “Code and
18 Data availability” section of this manuscript) and it is also available online ready to be
19 used in <https://biodama.shinyapps.io/rankspa/>.

20
21 RANKSPA consists of one page where: (1) On the **left side**, the user can upload
22 the input files and select one of the parameters that is needed for the cluster analysis
23 (“*Fraction of the total population*”, see the section “*Pipeline for ranking spatial areas*”
24 of the manuscript); (2) And on the **right side** of the page, there are seven tabs, where
25 the results of the different statistical analyses carried out and the maps created by the
26 application, can be visualized and downloaded. *Figure 2* shows the RANKSPA
27 application, once the simulated data (see *Code and Data availability* section of the
28 manuscript), has been processed and specifically showing the tab corresponding to the
29 map of relative risks.

31 *Input data*

32
33 First, we upload the data file by clicking the ‘Data input’ button and selecting
34 the corresponding file. The file must be an .xlsx file with the following columns:

- 35
- 36 ■ ID: Identification code of the spatial areas.
- 37 ■ population: Total population in each spatial area.
- 38 ■ Obs: Observed cases in each spatial area.
- 39 ■ Exp: Expected cases in each spatial area.

40
41 Second, we upload the map file containing the areas of the region of study. The
42 map file needs to be in shapefile format (.shp, .prj, .dbf, .shx) and The ID area should
43 be a unique identifier and should match with the ID area we specify for the data. The
44 map files can be uploaded by clicking the “Shp Input” button and selecting all the
45 corresponding files.

46
47 After uploading the map and the data files we can specify one option related to
48 the cluster analysis of the pipeline, the maximum fraction of the total population inside
49 the cluster. The default value is 15%.

1 *Start analysis button*

2
3 After uploading all the files and selecting the option for the cluster analysis, we
4 click the “Process” button. When we do this, the application starts to perform the
5 analysis of the pipeline.

6
7 *Results tabs*

8
9 The results of the analyses are shown in seven tabs. In the **first** one, “Ranking
10 Map”, a map of the areas belonging to the region of study is shown, displaying in colour
11 only those areas that are relevant according to the ranking criteria of the pipeline
12 describe before (areas with PP higher or equal to 80% and ranked first by the DOE and
13 second by the WRR). Moreover, the colour scale used in the map (see the legend)
14 corresponds to the sextiles of the absolute measures of risk (DOE) of the spatial areas.
15 The numbers shown inside the spatial units correspond to the identification code ID
16 (see description of the variables included in the Ranking Table tab). The application
17 allows users to zoom in on the map and also download it in pdf format.

18
19 In the **second tab**, “Ranking Table”, a table is shown containing the relative
20 and absolute risk estimates for the coloured areas in the map of the previous tab as well
21 as information about whether these areas are located within a spatial cluster (the
22 application allows users to download the table in .xlsx format). Specifically, the
23 estimators and variables shown in the table are:

- 24
- 25 ■ ranking: Ranking position (number 1 means the highest level of importance).
 - 26 ■ ID: Identification code of the spatial areas.
 - 27 ■ population: Total population in each spatial area.
 - 28 ■ Obs: Observed cases in each spatial area.
 - 29 ■ Exp: Expected cases in each spatial area.
 - 30 ■ SMR: Standard mortality/morbidity ratio (Observed/Expected)
 - 31 ■ Diff_obs_exp: Difference between observed and expected cases (DOE).
 - 32 ■ RR: Relative Risk.
 - 33 ■ lCre: Lower limit of the RR Credible Interval.
 - 34 ■ uCre: Upper limit of the RR Credible Interval.
 - 35 ■ PP: Posterior probability (PP) that $RR > 1$
 - 36 ■ cluster_1 to cluster_n: cluster membership (cluster=belongs to a cluster;
37 center=belongs to a cluster and is the central area)
- 38

39 Only the significant clusters by Kuldorff test ($p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$) are shown and
40 the order of appearance in the table is established according to the kuldorff statistic, so
41 that the cluster that present the highest Kulldorff statistic is the first (cluster_1). There
42 are some aspects related to multiple comparisons that are not taken into account in this
43 section, see (28).

44
45 In the **third tab**, “Spatial Tests”, the results from the spatial tests described in
46 the pipeline section of the manuscript are shown. The application displays exactly the
47 output given by R Software.

1 In the **fourth and fifth tabs**, “RR Map” and “PP Map” respectively, Relative
2 risks (RR) (smoothed standardized mortality ratios) and the distributions of posterior
3 probabilities (PP) of having an $RR > 1$ are mapped.

4
5 In the **sixth tab**, “Cluster Analysis”, the results from the cluster analysis are
6 shown according to the criteria described in the pipeline section of the manuscript. On
7 the left side of the tab, a table with the significant clusters in Kuldorff test (p-value
8 ≤ 0.05) are shown, and the order of appearance in the table is established according to
9 the kuldorff statistic, so that the cluster that present the highest Kulldorff statistic is the
10 first (cluster_1). Specifically, the estimators and variables shown in the table are:

- 11
- 12 ■ cluster: Identification numerical code for the cluster.
- 13 ■ size: Number of spatial units included in the cluster.
- 14 ■ statistic: Value of the Kulldorff statistic.
- 15 ■ pvalue: p-value from Kuldorff test.
- 16

17 Two maps are also shown in this tab, displaying in colour those spatial units
18 belonging to the cluster 1 and 2 described in the table on the left side of the tab. The
19 spatial units which correspond to the center of the clusters shown are coloured in a
20 darker grey than the rest.

21
22 In the **seventh tab**, “Complete Result Table”, a table is shown containing the
23 relative and absolute risk estimates for the all the areas in the map as well as information
24 about whether these areas are located within a spatial cluster (the application allows
25 users to download the table in .xlsx format). The estimators and variables shown are
26 the same as those contained in the table in second tab.

27
28 Finally, zoom in all the maps is available. User should select the area pressing
29 the left mouse button and make left double click over the area selected. To undo the
30 zoom applied, users should make left double click over the map.

31 *Example with simulated data*

32
33
34 The simulated data (“*data_example.xlsx*” and “*map_example.zip*”) described
35 before of observed and expected cases in 314 spatial areas and a shapefile (see section
36 “*Code and Data availability*” of the manuscript) were analyzed using RANKSPA
37 application using the default value for the fraction of the total population parameter.
38 The results obtained are shown in the Results section of the manuscript.

39 *Example with real data*

40
41
42 We have performed the pipeline to real data using the RANKSPA application.
43 It consisted in individual death entries (Observed cases) between 2005 and 2009 in men
44 in Galicia (North-East of Spain) (a region where there is a clear spatial pattern of lung
45 cancer mortality (8)) corresponding to lung cancer (International Classification of
46 Diseases, 10th Revision: C61), broken down by municipality ($n = 314$). Population data
47 by town and age (18 age groups) in 2007, the midpoint of the study period, was obtained
48 from the Spanish municipal roll. The National Statistics Institute (Instituto Nacional de
49 Estadística-INE) of Spain provided deaths and population data. The expected cases
50 were calculated by multiplying the overall Spanish age-specific mortality rates (using

1 lung cancer death entries between 2005 and 2009 in men for the whole country of Spain)
2 for the five-year study period by each town's person-years (2007 population * 5).
3 Afterward, standardized mortality ratios (SMRs) were computed as the ratios of the
4 observed to the expected deaths.

5
6 We selected lung cancer due to the high mortality and incidence of this chronic
7 disease. Lung cancer remains the leading cause of cancer incidence and mortality, with
8 2.1 million new lung cancer cases (11.6% of the total cases) and 1.8 million deaths
9 predicted in 2018 (18.4% of the total cancer deaths), representing close to 1 in 5 cancer
10 deaths (29)) which makes it possible to have credible indicators. Moreover, lung cancer
11 survival is poor, with a relative survival in Europe of 39% and 13% at 1 and 5 years
12 since diagnosis, respectively (30). In that way, lung cancer mortality is a good indicator
13 for monitoring this disease.

14
15 The results obtained using RANKSPA application to this data, using the default
16 value for the fraction of the total population parameter, are shown in Results section of
17 the manuscript.

20 Results

22 *Simulated data*

23
24 The results displayed in the tabs of RANKSPA application using simulated data
25 provided (see *Code and Data availability* section of the manuscript), are shown in
26 *Figure 3*. The tables shown in the "Ranking Table" and "Complete Result Table" tabs
27 are shown in Supplementary Material.

28
29 According with these results, there is a clear excess of mortality in the middle-
30 west of the studied area (see C and D sections in the *Figure 3*) where a spatial mortality
31 cluster is also located (see E section of *Figure 3*). Moreover, there are 5 spatial units
32 (IDs: 65, 293, 152, 305 and 156) located outside this cluster that occupy the top
33 positions in the ranking generated by the application (see A and B sections in the *Figure*
34 3).

35
36 According to the pipeline that implements the RANKSPA application, of the
37 total spatial units of the study region (314), only 14 have excess mortality whose PP
38 are greater than or equal to 80%. And all the spatial tests implemented except the
39 Moran's I test of spatial autocorrelation are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

40
41 Finally, in *Figure 4* a scatterplot is shown displaying the relationship between
42 DOE and WRR for simulated data in each spatial unit, and indicating when the PPs
43 were above or below 80%, which was one of the criteria to be taken into account in the
44 pipeline described above. It can be seen that there is in general a positive correlation
45 between absolute (DOE) and relative (WRR) measures. However, it is not so clear, or
46 at least a greater dispersion is observed when these measures take the highest values.

48 *Real data*

1 The results displayed in the tabs of RANKSPA application using real data are
2 shown in *Figure 5*. According with them, there is a clear excess of mortality in the west
3 of the region studied (see sections C and D of *Figure 5*) where several of the spatial
4 mortality clusters are also located (see E section of *Figure 5*). There are 3 spatial units
5 (IDs: 279, 53 and 33) located outside these clusters that occupy the top positions in the
6 ranking generated by the application (see A and B sections in the *Figure 5*).

7
8 Of the total spatial units of the study region (314), only 11 have excess mortality
9 whose PP are greater than or equal to 80%. And all the spatial tests implemented are
10 statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

11
12 Finally, in *Figure 4* a scatterplot is shown displaying the relationship between
13 DOE and WRR also for real data in each spatial unit, and indicating when the PP were
14 above or below 80%, which was one of the criteria to be taken into account in the
15 pipeline described above. It can be seen, as it was the case with the simulated data, that
16 there is in general a positive correlation between absolute (DOE) and relative (WRR)
17 measures. However, it is not so clear, or at least a greater dispersion is observed when
18 these measures take the highest values.

19 20 21 **Discussion**

22
23 In this paper we present a pipeline of analysis that could allow us to discriminate
24 regions of interest in the context of chronic diseases monitoring (like cancer monitoring)
25 by studying the spatial distribution in small areas of mortality / morbidity. It attends to
26 relative and absolute risk estimators and the precision of them, obtaining a ranking of
27 spatial units, thus being able to implement an initial spatial screening useful in
28 epidemiological surveillance and public health. Moreover, we present RANKSPA app,
29 a Shiny web application to implement this strategy in a simple way, fast and without a
30 deep technical knowledge of the statistical and programming methods necessary to
31 perform it. It also serves as an exploratory tool for spatial analysis since it enables
32 visualization of maps and the detection of clusters.

33
34 As already indicated in the Introduction section, in the context of public health
35 and surveillance of chronic diseases like cancer, the representation and analysis of maps
36 of events (disease mapping) within a fixed time frame/period is a basic tool and the
37 existence of criteria to discriminate relevant results is important. Furthermore in many
38 cases, this process should not only take into account relative measures, but also absolute
39 measures of risk. The pipeline shown tries to incorporate and integrate different aspects
40 already known in the field of space surveillance, combining these risk measures.

41
42 Here we have focused on the difference between observed and expected cases
43 (DOE) and the weighted relative risk (WRR) to rank areas. However, this is a first
44 approach and other measures that take into account the size of the region could be used
45 as the DOE will likely depend on the population of the areas. For this reason, other
46 relative measures that take into account the size of the areas (such as Chi-square
47 distances between observed and expected) and their associated uncertainty could be
48 considered when ranking the areas. Our preliminary assessment of such measures
49 indicates that the ranking is very similar to that provided by the DOE.

1
2 On the other hand, RANKSPA app, that is an open-source tool implemented
3 using R, Shiny and incorporating the functions from several R packages, is easy to use
4 and allows health researchers to perform all the analyses of the pipeline without the
5 need of having advanced statistical or programming skills. And since the proposed
6 methods for the initial screening that the pipeline can allow, are very common in
7 surveillance, researchers that need to perform more complex analyses should use other
8 statistical packages or other more complete and complex applications like
9 *SpatialEpiApp* (4).

10 In relation to the application of RANKSPA app to data, it is worth mentioning,
11 that the greater or lesser utility of the results it provides may depend largely on spatial
12 heterogeneity. When this is very large or there is no heterogeneity, it can be expected
13 that the discrimination of areas of interest through the described pipeline is not so easy
14 to interpret or is not useful. Moreover, in which ranges of heterogeneity may be useful
15 will also depend on the spatial distribution of the disease. Therefore, the results
16 obtained when using the RANKSPA application must be carefully evaluated taking into
17 account all these aspects. For reasons of time and space in this work no results are
18 presented analyzing other possible situations. Further studies are necessary to address
19 other types of scenarios where changes in the pipeline could surely be found and
20 proposed to provide a useful response in these contexts.

21
22 The real data used of lung cancer mortality represent a good example where the
23 results may be useful in monitoring this disease. There is some spatial heterogeneity,
24 with a clear and located spatial pattern. However, at the highest values of the risk
25 measures, the ranking of the space units depends very much on which measure of risk
26 (absolute (as implemented directly in the RANKSPA application) or relative (the table
27 shown in the RANKSPA app allows this visualization quickly) is taken into account
28 first.

29
30 As a general conclusion, the work presented shows a strategy of analysis to
31 implement an initial screening of disease risk that allows to discriminate regions of
32 interest by studying the spatial distribution in small areas, focused primarily on chronic
33 diseases such as cancer, where the proposed methods are commonly used in their
34 monitoring. And a shiny application that has been created to be able to implement this
35 strategy in a simple way, fast and without a deep technical knowledge of the statistical
36 and programming methods necessary to perform it.

37 **Code and Data availability**

- 38
39 • Pipeline R-code:
40 ○ R_script.R ([https://doi.org/ 10.6084/m9.figshare.11635908](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.11635908))
41
42
43 • RANKSPA R-shiny code:
44 ○ RANKSPA.zip ([https://doi.org/ 10.6084/m9.figshare.11635935](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.11635935))
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47 • Simulated data:

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- 2 ○ data_example.xlsx (<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.11467749>)
- 3
- 4 • Shapefiles:
- 5
- 6 ○ map_example.zip (<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.11467755>)
- 7

8 **Software availability**

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- 10 • <https://biodama.shinyapps.io/rankspa/>
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24 **Footnote**

25

26 *Conflicts of Interest:* The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

27

28 *Ethics Statement:* The authors are accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring
29 that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are
30 appropriately investigated and resolved.

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Figures captions

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10 **Figure 1.** Steps of the pipeline for the ranking of spatial areas

Figure 2. RANKSPA application overview.

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Figure 3. Results displayed in the tabs of RANKSPA application using simulated data. A) Ranking Map tab; B) Ranking Table tab; C) RR Map tab; D) PP Map tab; E) Cluster Analysis tab.

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Figure 4. Scatterplots displaying the relationship between weighted Relative Risk (WRR) and the difference between the observed and expected cases (DOE) in simulated and real data, indicating when the posterior probability (PPs) were above or below 80%.

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Figure 5. Results displayed in the tabs of RANKSPA application using real data. A) Ranking Map tab; B) Ranking Table tab; C) RR Map tab; D) PP Map tab; E) Cluster Analysis tab.